

Cognitive edge-cloud with serverless computing

Welcome to our 8th Newsletter!

As we step into 2025, it is a great time to look back on the remarkable achievements of the past year and set our sights on the opportunities ahead. The journey so far has been inspiring, fueled by the dedication and collaboration of our partners.

In this edition, we are excited to share the most recent updates from the EDGELESS project, including key milestones achieved and advancements made in strengthening security and protecting critical infrastructures.

We hope you enjoy this newsletter and invite you to stay connected with us online for ongoing updates about our activities and successes!

Our Latest Highlights

The banner features the EDGELESS logo on the left, with the text 'Info Day ONLINE' in large white font on the right. Below the title, it specifies the date 'Tuesday, November 26th, 2024' and the time '13:00-16:00 CET'. The background is a dark purple cityscape at night. The central section is titled 'Invited Projects' and displays logos for EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu, SovereignEDGE.eu COGNIT, AC³ (AGE AND COGNITIVE CLOUD EDGE CONTINUUM MANAGEMENT), COGNIFOG, MLSysOps, CloudSkin, ACES, and NOUS. At the bottom, there is a European Union flag logo and text stating: 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement No 101092950.'

The 1st EDGELESS Info Day took place on November 26th, 2024, in a virtual setting, marking a milestone for the project. Organized by the EDGELESS Project, this event provided attendees with a comprehensive overview of the project's objectives, innovative features, and significant progress achieved thus far. A total of 61 participants joined the webinar, demonstrating strong interest in the project's activities and advancements.

The Info Day was a resounding success, showcasing the project's cutting-edge developments while fostering active participation and collaboration across the cloud-edge continuum community. The contributions of invited projects added depth to the discussions, reflecting the collaborative spirit of the European research ecosystem.

Explore Our Zenodo Community

The **EDGELESS Zenodo Community** is your one-stop repository for all the resources and materials related to our project. This platform houses a comprehensive collection of our publications, public deliverables, presentations, and other valuable outputs.

Discover EDGELESS Demos on YouTube

The **EDGELESS YouTube channel** hosts an extensive collection of demos, offering a detailed view of the solutions and innovations developed throughout the project. These videos provide insights into the technical advancements and practical applications of our work in cybersecurity and edge computing.

Be sure to visit regularly for updates and share your favorite demos to help spread awareness of our work!

Our Latest Articles

Statelets – An novel state management approach in EDGELESS with mixed consistency models

The EDGELESS system seeks to bridge the gap between edge computing and the cloud by extending the serverless paradigm across the entire computational spectrum.

Rethinking the Mobile Edge for Vehicular Services

Connected cars (hereafter cars) and Cellular Vehicle-to-Everything (C-V2X) services – such as assisted and remote driving – are among the most promising use cases for 5G and Beyond-5G (B5G) networks.

EDGELESS Internet of Robotics Things Application Use Case

The Internet of Robotic Things (IoRT) use case showcases how EDGELESS integrates autonomous robotics and IoT-connected devices in agile manufacturing environments.

CONSORTIUM

The project unites **12 partners** from **6 European countries**, encompassing the necessary expertise to successfully accomplish the project's ambitious goals.

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